

Coulometric Titration of Niobium in EDTA Complexing Solution

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Constant current coulometry of Nb in EDTA was studied employing both potentiometric and amperometric end-point techniques. The titrations were based on the oxidation of Nb(IV)-EDTA with electrogenerated Fe(III) at a graphite anode. The rate of disproportionation of Nb(IV)-EDTA was found to be slow enough not to affect the accuracy sought for the titration. The coulometric titration of Nb in EDTA was found to be more accurate than in 1F sulfuric acid. The mean error in the titrations of 4.76 to 19.65 mg of Nb in a volume of about 100 ml of 0.02 to 0.04F EDTA was 0.13%. It was found that Ta may be tolerated to a ratio of 1 : 4, Ta : Nb, in a solution containing 13 mg of Nb.

RESULTS from the coulometric titration¹ of Nb in 1F sulfuric acid do not have the precision and accuracy sought in the analysis of Nb. Furthermore, difficulties with the relatively slow reduction of Nb(V) to Nb(III), the tendency of Nb(V) to form colloidal solutions in sulfuric acid, and the desirability of determining Nb in the presence of Ta which is invariably present in Nb ores led this author to study the coulometry of Nb in EDTA complexing solution. The titration is based on the reaction between electrogenerated Fe(III) and Nb(IV)-EDTA.

$\text{Nb(IV)-EDTA} + \text{Fe(III)} \rightarrow \text{Nb(V)-EDTA} + \text{Fe(II)}$. The polarographic data of several workers²⁻⁴ who studied the determination of Nb in EDTA solution, especially that of Kirby and Freiser⁵ were exploited in designing this titration.

Experimental

Apparatus. The apparatus used for the coulometric titration and for detection of the end point has been described previously¹, except that the bridge and the anode compartment of Cell B were filled with saturated K_2SO_4 solution. The amperometric end point detection system consisting of two polarized (1-cm².) Pt electrodes was employed even though it was realized that the Pt surface might catalyze the reaction between H^+ and Nb(IV)-EDTA. With 0.15 volt impressed on the electrodes only a slight residual current flowed before the end point, but thereafter the current increased due to the following reactions :

The potentiometric end point detection system employed Hg pool and saturated Hg_2SO_4 (S. M. E.) electrodes. The potentiometric end point was employed because steady current readings could not be obtained by the amperometric method.

Reagents. Solutions of Nb(V) and Ta(V) in potassium hydroxide were prepared from Nb_2O_5 (99.85%) and Ta_2O_5 (9.51%) as described by Kirby and Freiser^{5,6}. Nb(V)-EDTA solutions were prepared by mixing an aliquot of Nb(V) solution (10^{-3} F in 2F KOH) with 25 ml of 0.1F EDTA and 25 ml of saturated K_2SO_4 solution. The pH was adjusted to the desired value by the addition of 1F H_2SO_4 . The solution was boiled for 30 sec. and cooled to room temperature before it was transferred to the coulometric cell¹.

Procedure. The Nb(V)-EDTA solution was deaerated with N_2 , then reduced at a stirred Hg cathode maintained at a potential of -1.4 to -1.6 volts vs. S. M. E. for 3 to 4 hr.

Results and Discussion

Controlled Potential Coulometry. In order to establish a coulometric method for determination of Nb, controlled potential coulometry was investigated first. The controlled potential coulometry of Nb(V) in EDTA has not been utilized previously except to check^{3,5} the polarographic "n" value. The ratio of the diffusion current to background current proved to be small for an accurate controlled potential reduction of Nb(V)-EDTA. The ratio was favourable (150 : 1) for the controlled potential oxidation of Nb(IV)-EDTA, but the oxidation took considerably longer time than the reduction. The study of the determination of Nb on the basis of the oxidation of Nb(IV)-EDTA at controlled potential was not refined because the results in the constant current coulometric titration were found to be satisfactory.

Constant Current Coulometry. Several variables for the reduction of Nb(IV)-EDTA solutions preparatory to constant current coulometric determination of Nb were studied : (1) *Potential of stirred Hg cathode for reduction*, (2) *Effect of pH*, and (3) *Time interval for reduction*.

Polarograms of Nb(V)-EDTA were taken whenever any variable was studied. The K_2SO_4 agar bridge and S. M. E. used in the polarography were the same as those used in the coulometry.

Potential of Stirred Mercury Cathode for reduction. The values of half-wave potentials of Nb(V) solutions containing $4.00 \times 10^{-3} M$ Nb(V), $0.02 M$ EDTA and $0.2 M K_2SO_4$ at pH 3, 4 and 5 were respectively -1.22 volts, -1.25 volts and -1.31 volts D. M. E. vs. S. M. E. for the reduction of Nb(V) to Nb(IV) in EDTA solutions. Consequently, the potential of the stirred Hg cathode was maintained manually from -1.4 to -1.6 volts vs. S. M. E. for the reduction of Nb(V)-EDTA solution. At this potential range no electro-generation of Nb(III) occurs, since the second wave due to reduction of Nb(IV) and Hydrogen ion does not start to rise until -1.63 volts Hg vs. S. M. E. at pH 3 and 4.

Effect of pH. The reduction of Nb(V)-EDTA solution was studied at pH 3, 4 and 5. Since precipitation occurred in $0.02 M$ EDTA solution at pH 2 during adjustment of the pH by $1 F H_2SO_4$, reduction was not carried out in this range. It was found that the initial current due to reduction of Nb(V)-EDTA complex at pH 5 was considerably lower than at pH 3 and 4. This necessitated a longer time for the reduction of Nb(V) solution at pH 5. The data given in Table 1 indicated that a suitable pH for the reduction of Nb(V)-EDTA is from 3 to 4.

TABLE 1—THE EFFECT OF pH ON THE COULOMETRIC DETERMINATION OF Nb(IV)-EDTA SOLUTION^a

pH	Nb Taken (mg)	Nb Found (mg)	Percent Error
5.0	4.76	4.55	-4.41
5.0	4.76	4.54	-4.62
5.0	4.76	4.49	-5.67
4.0	4.76	4.76	0.00
4.0	4.76	4.77	+0.21
4.0	4.76	4.70	-1.26
3.0	4.76	4.75	-0.21
3.0	4.76	4.75	-0.21
3.0	4.76	4.70	-1.26

^aPrior reduced from Nb(V)-EDTA at -1.4 to -1.6 volts vs. S.M.E. for 3-4 hr.

Time Interval for Reduction. Whenever the current of the reduction solution equals the residual current of the blank solution, it can ordinarily be concluded that the electro-reduction of the reducible ion in a solution is complete. This criterion could not be employed because the initial currents due to reduction of Nb(V)-EDTA at pH 3 and 4 are not high enough as compared to the residual currents. Consequently, the time required for the complete electroreduction of Nb(V)-EDTA was determined empirically. It follows from the data in Table 2 that 3 to 4 hr are sufficient for the reduction of Nb(V)-EDTA. The high results obtained after reduction for 10 and 12.5 hr may be anticipated from the kinetic studies. The kinetics of the chemical change of Nb(IV)-

TABLE 2—THE EFFECT OF REDUCTION TIME ON THE COULOMETRIC TITRATION OF NB IN EDTA SOLUTION AT A pH=3.5

Reduction Time (hrs.)	Nb Taken (mg)	Nb Found (mg)	Percent Error
2	4.76	4.55	-4.41
2	4.76	4.51	-5.25
3	4.91	4.92	+0.20
3	4.91	4.89	-0.41
4	4.91	4.92	+0.20
4	4.91	4.90	-0.20
10	4.91	4.96	+1.02
10	4.91	4.99	+1.63
12.5	4.91	5.27	+7.33
12.5	4.91	5.46	+11.2

EDTA was studied at pH 3 and 4. Spectrophotometry was found to be more sensitive than ordinary D. C. Polarography to follow the reaction kinetics. The rate of reaction was followed by measuring the absorbance due to Nb(V)-EDTA at 226-228 nm because its absorbance was much greater than that of Nb(IV)-EDTA which absorbs at 285-290 nm. It was found that the reaction rate is second order with respect to Nb(IV). From the spectrophotometric evidence it was concluded that Nb(IV)-EDTA undergoes a disproportionation to Nb(III) and Nb(IV)-EDTA complexes. However, this reaction occurs at such a slow rate in the $5 \times 10^{-4} M$ to $2 \times 10^{-3} M$ Nb solution that the accuracy in the coulometric determination is not affected within the limits sought in this work. The results shown in Table 3 are typical.

TABLE 3—COULOMETRIC TITRATION OF Nb(IV)-EDTA^a AT $12^\circ \pm 2^\circ$ USING POTENTIOMETRIC OR AMPEROMETRIC END POINTS

Nb Taken (mg)	Nb Found (mg)	Percent Error
4.76	4.74	-0.42
4.91	4.90	-0.20
4.76	4.73	-0.63
4.91	4.91	0.00
4.91	4.92	+0.20
9.71	9.67	-0.41
9.71	9.77	+0.62
9.83	9.96	+1.32
9.83	9.76	-0.71
19.05	18.99	-0.31
19.05	19.16	+0.58
19.65	19.54	-0.56
19.65	19.73	+0.41
Mean per cent error = -0.13		

^aSee note under Table 1.

Interference: Effect of presence of Ta (V). It was concluded that Ta (V) was reduced¹ in H_2SO_4 by exhaustive electrolysis at the Hg cathode, and interfered in the constant current coulometric determination of Nb. The problem of determining Nb in the presence of Ta was solved in EDTA complexing solutions. Freiser and Kirby⁶ reported that Ta (V)-EDTA was reduced at a dropping mercury cathode. Since the half-wave potential varied from -1.23 to -1.26 volts vs. S. C. E. in

the pH region of 3.3 to 5.6, the Ta (V) complex should not be reduced at the stirred Hg cathode, if its potential is maintained at about -1.4 volts vs. S. M. E. In fact it was found that the Ta (V)-EDTA solution was not reduced even by exhaustive electrolysis for 10 hr. Thus Nb can be titrated without interference in the presence of Ta. Table 4 shows typical results. The concentration of Ta (V) could not be increased beyond the value given in Table 4 because the turbidity due to the precipitation of Ta (V) which appeared during the adjustment of pH, might result in the coprecipitation of Nb (V).

TABLE 4—THE COULOMETRIC TITRATION OF Nb(IV)—EDTA^a IN THE PRESENCE OF TA (V)-EDTA AT 12° ± 2° USING POTENTIOMETRIC END POINT DETECTION

Period of Electrolysis (hrs.)	Ta Taken (mg)	Nb Taken (mg)	Nb Found (mg)	Percent Error (Niobium)
12	2.89	9.53	9.58	+0.52
3	2.89	13.34	13.23	-0.82
4	1.93	4.76	4.78	+0.42
4	0.96	4.76	4.76	0.00

^aSee note in Table 1.

Conclusions

It has been shown that niobium can be determined coulometrically in presence of Ta. This method is more accurate and convenient than the volumetric methods⁷⁻⁹ because the titrant is generated *in situ*. This eliminates the problem of preparation, standardization and storage of the titrant. Furthermore, the amount of this reagent is measured in terms of accurately known fundamental quantities (current, time, and Faraday constant) rather than from the volume used.

Evaluation of Errors: The two lots of Nb₂O₅ used in this work were labeled 99.85% pure by the supplier. Both contained some greyish-black particles which were removed mechanically as far as possible before drying a sample. The weight of the residue left after dissolving the cold melt was negligible when compared to the weight of Nb₂O₅ taken. The solution of Nb₂O₅ in KOH became slightly colloidal, but the amount of Nb which underwent such a change could not be readily evaluated. The samples of Nb were taken volumetrically rather than by weight because of the experimental difficulty involved in preparation of Nb solutions. The samples comprised 25 to 50 ml of standard Nb solution taken by a calibrated pipet. The accuracy of the volume transferred was one to two parts per thousand. Errors introduced in the procedures during the adjustment of pH of Nb (V)-EDTA solution and in its subsequent boiling are presumed to be negligible. Some local precipitation can result when 1F H₂SO₄ acid is added to Nb (V)-EDTA solution. This was minimized by efficient stirring when the acid

was added slowly. Purified N₂, required to deaerate the solution and to maintain an inert atmosphere in the cell was supplied at a reasonable rate so that the solution would not be carried by spray through the N₂ exit or adhere to the sides of the electrolytic cell and to various components in it. Some Nb can be lost through diffusion from the catholyte to the bridge compartment. This was minimized by keeping the level of the anolyte higher than the level of the catholyte. A rough experimental estimate of the loss due to ion transport from the catholyte to the bridge was found to be about three parts per million, which seems low.

A number of errors were associated with the electrical measurements. An important error in this case is due to measurement of time. The synchronous motor electric interval timer could be read to one-tenth of a second and would exhibit error in starting and stopping. The timer was calibrated with a crystal controlled interval meter by Transistor Specialities (Model 361). It was found that readings of 60 to 3,000 sec. are accurate well within one-tenth of a second. To decrease the error due to timing, the time interval for a typical titration was increased to 600 sec. by lowering the value of the constant current near the end point. A standard resistor of 50 ohms certified to 5 parts per ten thousand was used at room temperature. The voltage drop across the resistor was measured by a potentiometer, and did not vary more than 5 parts per ten thousand when 23 ma, and two parts per ten thousand when 4 ma, were passed through the cell.

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